

POLITICAL SCIENCES

FOREIGN POLICY CHALLENGES IN THE SOUTH CAUCASUS

Chavleishvili G.

International Relations, Ph.D student

Georgian Technical University

Tbilisi, Kostava #77, Georgia

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9344-858X>

Japharidze E.

Doctor of Political Sciences, Associate professor

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9239-4785>

Georgian Technical University, Tbilisi, Georgia

Abstract

The article discusses the challenges of foreign policy in the countries of the South Caucasus, which are conditioned by the historical confrontation between the dominant states. In the conditions of the formation of current international order, new interests are emerging in the South Caucasus. It is in the interest of the leading players that all three states of the South Caucasus ought to have different foreign policies, which is harmful for the goals of regional integration. For these purposes it is important to emphasize the February 2025 statement of the prime minister of Italy, Giorgia Meloni - European civilization is not only a geographical space, but also a set of values, which is born in the bosom of Greek philosophy, Roman law and Christian values. The mismatch of interests among the dominant players in the region leads to conflict. The South Caucasus region along with the purposeful use of new geopolitical and geoeconomic opportunities, is trying to ensure peaceful regional development. Accordingly, putting the Anaklia port issue on the agenda will lead to tension between the dominant players and the South Caucasus enters at the center of geopolitical obstacles. In this regard, it is important to note the March 2025 statement made by U.S secretary of state Marco Rubio - a new era is beginning for the South Caucasus. That is to say that Georgia is interesting to the West not as a separate player, but as an integral part of the „Transcaspiian International Transport Route“ and the “One Road, One Belt” project.

Keywords: South Caucasus; Regional integration; Foreign policy; Balance of power.

Introduction

After the collapse of the Soviet Union, the South Caucasus region was considered a closed space from a geopolitical point of view. The end of the cold war created a favorable situation for the Transcaucasian region, namely, as a result of the political conjuncture of that time, the South Caucasus regained the status of an economically important geographical unit, which laid the foundation for the development of regional coordination.

The end of the Cold War has created new opportunities for peace, democracy, and the spread of capitalism. However, as events unfolded, change proved difficult in Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Georgia, given the complex realities of post-Soviet transition (Rumer E. Sokolsky R. Stronski P. 2017, U.S. POLICY TOWARD THE SOUTH CAUCASUS pp.5). The collapse of the Soviet Union paved the way for the growing influence of two dominant states in the South Caucasus region, Türkiye and the Islamic Republic of Iran. The first years of independence in the South Caucasus were unstable, with conflicts rife throughout the region (Rumer E. Sokolsky R. Stronski P. 2017, pp.8). Türkiye has actively begun to spread its influence in the Republic of Georgia and the Republic of Azerbaijan, and the Islamic Republic of Iran - in the Republic of Armenia. As the development of the conflict has shown, the attitude of Türkiye in the Republic of Azerbaijan is multifaceted and comprehensive, both in cultural, political

and economic terms (Rumer E. Sokolsky R. Stronski P. 2017, pp.9).

It is noteworthy that in the post-Soviet period, relations among Georgia and Türkiye have been successfully developing in various areas, especially in the context of education and the economy, as well as in close military-technical cooperation (Marabyan K., 2014, *osobennosti sovremennoy politiki turtsii na yuzhnom kavkaze* pp.131, DOI 10.22394/2073-2929-2022-04-130-138). Türkiye uses flexible diplomacy, a strategy supported by its advantageous geopolitical location, strong military capabilities, and peaceful means of influence (e.g., soft power). This allows Türkiye to increase its influence, especially in Central Asia, the Middle East, and the South Caucasus. Since the 2000s, the geopolitical confrontation between west and east has shown trends that change the positioning of dominant states in relation to a particular region and shape different approaches (Sulaberidze Y. S. 2020, *kavkazskiy-vektor-politiki-irana-vchera-segodnya-zavtra* pp.143, pub: „Russian Colonial Studies“). After the 2001 crisis, Türkiye has significantly established itself among the twenty leading economies of the world (G20), which has led to the growth of state role of Türkiye. Official Ankara actively participates in financial and other investment activities in the Republic of Azerbaijan. (Marabyan K., 2014, *osobennosti sovremennoy politiki turtsii na yuzhnom kavkaze* pp.131, DOI 10.22394/2073-2929-2022-04-130-138).

Currently, a different approach is being developed in international relations, which essentially depends on the time and the corresponding development of events. The global significance and role of those institutions that ensured the maintenance or balancing of political and economic relations from the 1990s to the present day are changing. (Sulaberidze Y. S. 2020, *kavkazskiy-vektor-politiki-irana-vchera-segodnya-zavtra* pp.143, pub: „Russian Colonial Studies”). Recent geopolitical developments have led to the formation of a multipolar global landscape. The influence of Türkiye and the Islamic Republic of Iran in the region has significantly strengthened. Based on this perspective, the interests of the main players in the South Caucasus are rapidly growing and accordingly political and economic processes in the region depend on the positioning of the dominant actors. On the one hand, the growing activity of regional powers is due to the consolidation of historical influence and the restoration of their own national interests (Sulaberidze Y. S. 2020, pp.144). Under these circumstances we shall consider Robert Kagan's statement according to which when a democratic state itself weakens its global influence in the region, regional states create the weather (p'olit'ik'a (2020), *Politics and Democracy* pp.250 Tbilisi, pub: „intelekti”). The author also notes that regional states should not be criticized for not doing what they have never done before, since the fate of democracies is affected by changes in the geopolitical balance as a result of the behavior of the hegemonic state (pp. 251).

The issue of energy resources plays an important role in determining the foreign policy of the Republic of Armenia. In view of the latter, the state debt accumulated over time from the 1990s to the present day has forced the Republic of Armenia to transfer strategic facilities to the Russian Federation. It is worth noting that the Armenian Railway is owned by Russia.¹² Republic of Armenia has adopted the draft law on accession to the European Union in the second reading, which was initiated by a public petition. This marks the beginning of the process of the Republic of Armenia's accession to the European Union.¹³

Despite the existence of opposing foreign policy courses by the three states, the regional integration of Georgia, the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Armenia has political and economic importance. Georgia is not considered a state with natural resources, for these purposes the Republic of Azerbaijan possesses abundant oil reserves. In this regard, it is important to note the statement of president Ilham Aliyev of November 12, 2024. In his speech at the 10th Intergovernmental Commission on Economic Cooperation between Georgia and the Republic of Azerbaijan, the prime minister of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ali Asadov, emphasized that the development of strategic relations with Georgia is one of the main priorities of Azerbaijan's foreign policy, the legal basis of which includes 140 documents. According to prime minister Asadov, the Republic of Azerbaijan and Georgia are taking important steps to develop the political and economic potential of the region.¹⁴

Methods:

The article relies on several research methods used in international relations: content analysis, the case-study method, and comparative analysis, enabling a thorough examination of the various sources related to the research topic and the formulation of conclusions based on factual observation.

Results and Discussion

Against the backdrop of the challenges that have arisen over the years, the South Caucasus is facing a difficult situation not only in Georgia, but also in Republic of Armenia and Republic of Azerbaijan. A key feature of the region is the geopolitical backdrop, in which all three states are vulnerable and cooperation between them is essential in the interests of common security. Official Baku expects from official Yerevan a constitutional amendment on the issue of Karabakh. The influence of Türkiye in the South Caucasus grows noticeably, against the background of the fact that the leading powers try to reduce an influence of Russian Federation in the Transcaucasian region. With this in mind prof. Jeffrey Sachs advocates the 3+3 model of integration of the South Caucasus as a constructive and dynamic dialogue with the involvement of the dominant powers around the region. The latter should aim at common investment programs, sustainable development strategies and practical steps for regional development. However, regarding the outside world, the Colombian professor notes that they should exercise great prudence so as not to destabilize the situation in the region.

After the Islamic Revolution of 1979, Tehran explicitly declared its strategic interests in the South Caucasus. Islamic Republic of Iran has close historical ties to the region, which increases the activity of the Islamic Republic of Iran towards the South Caucasus region and the main features of its policy (Sulaberidze Y. S. 2020, *kavkazskiy-vektor-politiki-irana-vchera-segodnya-zavtra* pp.147, pub: „Russian Colonial Studies”). Experts on Iranian-Russian relations (including Mahir Khalifa-zadeh, Eduard Bagirov) develop the view that Iran should become a military ally of Russia, which in turn stems from the historical ties between the two states, geographical proximity, and the unification of two civilizational systems (Christianity, Islam). In addition, they are driven by a common goal: 1) the creation of a multi-level security system; 2) preventing the positioning of extra-regional players in the South Caucasus and Caspian regions (Sulaberidze Y. S. 2020, pp.147). Against the background of the adaptation of the role of an essential subject in modern economic and logistical projects, it is noticeable that the foreign policy goals of the Republic of Azerbaijan are quite difficult to achieve. With its significant reserves of natural resources, the Republic of Azerbaijan still maintains the role of an economically dominant country in the South Caucasus region, which is reflected in the involvement of official Baku in modern logistics and infrastructure projects. Georgia, with its geographical location and access to the sea, remains practically the only unproblematic route for China, through which China should be able to import products to Europe. The “One Belt, One Road” initiative, announced in Beijing

in 2013, aims to revive the historical land "Silk Road" and create a maritime trade route through the Indian Ocean, the Red Sea and the Mediterranean Sea to Europe, in particular to Venice. The project envisages the construction of ports, railways and highways, the introduction of innovations and the creation of a unified regulatory system under Chinese leadership, using Chinese capital and Chinese labor (Gachechiladze, R. (2018). *akhlo aghmosavleti. geop'olit'ik'a. t'omi 2*. pp.111 [Middle East. *Geopolitics*. Volume 2]. Tbilisi, pub: „Bakur Sulakhauri“).

Georgia has limited natural resources, however, Georgia's relief and geographical location determine, on the one hand, the potential for the country's economic-financial development, and on the other hand, the effective conduct of regional development. The Caucasian nation is the best manifestation of European historical-value values. The optimal option for the countries of the South Caucasus is if, in the course of the new global redistribution, the dominant players agree on balancing control over the South Caucasus regional space, for which the political and economic consolidation of the South Caucasus region becomes of key importance. Regarding the above, it is important to note the assessment of Prof. Jeffrey Sachs of Columbia University, expressed in the European Parliament on February 19, 2025 (Professor Jeffrey Sachs' speech in the European Parliament at an event titled "The Geopolitics of Peace", hosted by former U.N Assistant secretary general and current BSW MEP Michael von der Schulenburg, on February 19, 2025). During the meeting, he emphasized the great importance of constructive relations based on realism in modern geopolitics. The Columbia University professor shares the views of American political scientist John Mearsheimer the attitude according to which political realism is the conduct of a constructive dialogue based on bilateral international relations. Taking into account the above, with its modern financial and logistical potential, Georgia can, based on its geopolitical role, acquire and conduct international relations both in the neighborhood and on an international scale. The key topic of the speech in the European Parliament was the "Black Sea Strategy", for which the Columbia University professor connected the concepts of Lord Palmerston, Zbigniew Brzezinski and Halford Mackinder (February 27 2025, Jeffrey Sachs in the European Parliament, *The Geopolitics of Peace - The Black Sea Strategy*). In terms of the regional integration it's important to emphasize Zbigniew Brzezinski's opinion in his 1997 book *U.S. Hegemony and Its Geostrategic Imperatives*, whereas the author describes the geopolitical fate of the Transcaucasian republics depends on whether Türkiye maintains its interest in Europe and whether the European Union accepts Türkiye as a member state. In addition, the Polish political scientist suggests that if the European Union refuses to accept Türkiye, then the South Caucasus region will depend on the specifics of the relationship between the Russian Federation and the European Union (BRZEZINSKI Z., (1997) *THE GRAND CHESSBOARD American Primacy and Its Geostrategic Imperatives* pp.47, pub: „Basic Books“).

Prof. Omer Turan prescribes, that on the foreign policy level, Türkiye is deeply embedded in the Syrian crisis. It has drifted away from its former EU membership bid and stopped acting as a regional actor providing stability. Türkiye is no longer able to have strong diplomatic relationships with South Caucasus' governments and offer them some new perspectives to strengthen cooperation with each other (Turan Ö., 2019, *Two Modalities of Turkish Foreign and Domestic Policy: From Soft Power to War Rhetoric*, pp.48) Türkiye, which declares its support for Ukraine, in parallel with this, the Republic of Azerbaijan is developing interstate relations with the Russian Federation. The statement of Türkiye is one nation, two states. The dominant powers that have an interest in the South Caucasus might consider that events in the South Caucasus should not develop like events in the territory of Syria. As a result of this conflict, it is noticeable that Türkiye is becoming stronger. The assumption that Türkiye is increasingly focused on its own domestic politics and that issues related to regional stability and the South Caucasus are no longer important to Türkiye (Turan Ö., 2019). From our point of view this is not an accurate assumption, to put it another way Türkiye's interests in the South Caucasus are growing rapidly. In the new geopolitical reality, regional integration is noteworthy for the security purposes of the South Caucasus, for which strong political and economic cooperation between the three countries of Transcaucasia is required. The latter creates a solid consolidation of the three states of the South Caucasus or a regional heavy background.

At the 78th session of the United Nations General Assembly in 2023, important statements were made regarding the peaceful resolution of hostilities in Ukraine and the tense situation between Republic of Armenia and Republic of Azerbaijan, which was noted at the UN session as the most important challenge facing the South Caucasus region. The statements made by the leaders of a number of leading countries speaking at the session once again revealed the importance and necessity of increasing the UN Action Plan, the composition and capacity of the security council. The meeting emphasized the importance of discussing the issue of UN structural reform in various formats (David Aghmashenebeli National Defence Academy of Georgia, 2023. pp.21, ISBN:9789941861697).

It is important to note the political actions of France in the South Caucasus, for which the Republic of Armenia has become its fulcrum in the region. In recent years, there has been an attempt to establish influence in the Republic of Azerbaijan. Another important thing to remember is the official Baku response on December 27, 2023, to declare two representatives of the French Embassy persona non grata and recall them from the Republic of Azerbaijan, which qualifies as a practical manifestation of the sovereign position of the Republic of Azerbaijan.¹⁵ It is consieved that the fundamental aspects of a sovereign state are: legislation, tax policy, and the education system. Therefore, we conceive that politics is a technology to realize national interests, while geopolitics is deemed to be a technology to achieve pragmatic interests in accordance with sovereign will of nation.

Professor Edisher Japaridze describes the expansion of the European Union's policy towards the South Caucasus in all areas, which was a prerequisite for the neighborhood policy and cooperation. In his work "Contemporary Challenges of the European Union Neighborhood Policy in the South Caucasus", assuming that the enlargement of the European Union had a historical and political significance for the states of geographical Europe. The mentioned action plan was a political step between the European Union and the South Caucasus, which determined cooperation not only in political terms, but also in economic, legal and other areas (JAPHARIDZE E. (2021), *MODERNE HERAUSFORDERUNGEN DER NACHBARSCHAFTSPOLITIK VON EU IM SÜDKAUKASUS* pp.6. pub: "Universali"). To put it another way European experience shows that even the beginning of moving towards a goal changes relations among states (Ashervudi. S., P'inder, J. (2018). *evrok'avshiris dzalian mok'le shesavali* pp.196. meotkhe gamotsema, *The European Union a very short introduction fourth edition*, Tbilisi). The European Union and Republic of Armenia have significantly strengthened their partnership and cooperation. In February 2024 the parties began working on new partnership agenda among the EU and Republic of Armenia.¹⁶

It is noteworthy that if the dominant state's policy encounters insurmountable obstacles along the way, it confronts them philosophically and tries to adapt to them. If it believes that the opposing force is stronger, it is willing to retreat on certain sections of the diplomatic front and resort to a more rational logic and rhetoric of power. (p'olit'ik'a (2020), *Politics and Democracy* Kenan G., 2015, *sabchouri martvis saTaveebi* pp. 120). In such a situation, losing self-control does not help strengthen one's position in politics (Kagan 2015, pp.121). It is worth noting that George Kennan concludes in his work that Soviet influence on the free institutions of the western world cannot be contained by appeals and speeches. This is possible only through tireless resistance, which is constantly changing. Later, Francis Fukuyama describes the actions of the People's Republic of China in his book and concludes that although some modern countries may not achieve stable liberal democracy, and others may revert to other, more primitive forms of government, such as theocracy or military dictatorship, the ideal of liberal democracy cannot be improved upon. (Fukuyama F., 1992, *The End of History*, pp.15 https://d11.cuni.cz/plugin-file.php/1105281/mod_resource/content/1/Fukuyama%20-%20The%20End%20of%20History%20and%20the%20Last%20Man.pdf).

Recent developments reveal the activities of Türkiye in the South Caucasus. It is noteworthy that in 2009, at the initiative of official Ankara, the Organization of Turkic States was established, the members of which are: Türkiye, the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Kyrgyz Republic, the Republic of Tajikistan and the Republic of Uzbekistan. At the ministerial, the above-mentioned countries adopted a joint action plan - the "Ankara Declaration", one of the main issues of which is the issue of strengthening the Trans-Caspian international transport route (known as

the Middle Corridor). In this regard, the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Türkiye, Hakan Fidan, expressed his position: "The Middle Corridor is the shortest and safest trade route from Europe to Asia, the potential of which we must use well." Among the priority projects discussed was the issue of increasing the capacity of the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway.¹⁷

Conclusion

The current geopolitical situation shows that diversification is inevitable for small countries. The regional integration of Georgia, the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Armenia should not be based on the format of a military-militaristic bloc, but on a model of political-economic integration, the main goal of which should be open multilateral vectors in the economic-financial context. During the meeting between U.S secretary of state Marco Rubio and foreign minister of Türkiye Hakan Fidan, the role of Türkiye as the geopolitical position of the U.S in the South Caucasus was noted, which reveals the regional importance of the Republic of Azerbaijan. It is worth noting that the West prioritizes the Black Sea geopolitical area considering the strategic importance of Black Sea. In light of eastern European countries demonstrate a different approach to regional policy in the South Caucasus. Moreover, the Black Sea is of geopolitical interest for Türkiye and for the Russian Federation.

There are three main components for the regional development of the South Caucasus. First of all, close political and economic coordination among the three states of the South Caucasus is necessary. Secondly it is important to determine the vectors of foreign policy of Georgia, the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Armenia, which should be aimed at regional development. The third issue should be the improvement of constructive relations with the European space, since the issue of the Anaklia port can improve the regional background in the South Caucasus and the Black Sea basin countries, which in turn will simplify transportation between Europe and Asia. We shall emphasize that international relations require the settlement of interstate relations through mutual agreement and dialogue. Therefore, it is obvious to acknowledge the February 2025 statement of the prime minister of Italy Giorgia Meloni, which describes for us that the European values are what we uphold. Regarding the Anaklia port, it is important to emphasize that this port increases Georgia's regional and geopolitical importance, which in turn strengthens the regional security of the South Caucasus. The April 2025 visit of the Georgian delegation to the United States (which was initiated by the U.S Embassy in Georgia), during which the Georgian side met with Joshua Hack, Deputy Assistant Secretary of State for South Caucasus Affairs to U.S Secretary of State Marco Rubio, confirms that the South Caucasus is considered as an integral space of modern logistical and economic projects for the United States.

For the purposes of regional integration, we shall note that on June 2024 meeting which was held in Tbilisi to discuss cooperation and foreign policy challenges in the South Caucasus region. On the event there were international analysts from various states, including from Georgia, from Republic of Azerbaijan and

from Republic of Armenia It was discussed how the South Caucasus should become a politically important region and whether it is possible for the region to use the prospects of an idea of regional integration. Historical observation reveals that there have been numerous attempts at deep cooperation between the countries from the Transcaucasian Federation, to the Caucasian Benelux model, although these projects were not successful at all. In the context of the ongoing geopolitical transformation in the world, the South Caucasus region should become a crossroads where the world's main communication channels will pass. For regional purposes, it is worth noting that the Black Sea coastline is an important geopolitical asset for Georgia. The latter, in turn, is in the interests of dominant players (including: the Islamic Republic of Iran, the United States of America, Türkiye, the Russian Federation, the People's Republic of China). It is noteworthy for the foreign policy of the South Caucasus countries that an alliance with a dominant state does not mean that it does not consider the configuration of the allied state to create a more favorable positioning for itself.

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